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ADVANCES IN ACCELERATION SENSITIVITY MEASUREMENT AND MODELING

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Abstract: The effects of acceleration on "precision" frequency sources have recently been reviewed by the IEEE Standards Project P1193 Committee. Acceleration effects in "less precise" frequency sources (UHF and microwave sources such as SAW resonator and delay line oscillators, as well as VCXO modulation oscillators) are not addressed. Experience has shown that acceleration effects can be just as important and in some cases are more challenging to quantify in these other classes of devices. This paper discusses various aspects of measurement and modeling which have been discovered while working with these "less precise" devices, but do in fact have general application. The first part of this paper discusses the modeling of acceleration effects in BAW resonators and oscillators by means of equivalent electrical circuits. The second part of this paper discusses practical considerations in the measurement of UHF and microwave frequency sources. The final section of this paper presents a derivation of the general conditions for an intrinsically acceleration-insensitive crystal resonator and discusses the application of the conditions to the evaluation of the relative sensitivity of different crystal cuts, modes of motion, mounting geometries, and piezoelectric materials.

Introduction

The effects of acceleration on "precision" frequency sources have recently been reviewed by the IEEE Standards Project P1193 Committee [1]. Acceleration effects in "less precise" frequency sources (UHF and microwave sources such as SAW resonator and delay line oscillators, as well as VCXO modulation oscillators) are not addressed. Experience has shown that acceleration effects can be just as important and in some cases are more challenging to quantify in these other classes of devices. This paper discusses various aspects of measurement and modeling which have been

discovered while working with these "less precise" devices, but do in fact have general application.

The first part of this paper discusses the modeling of acceleration effects in BAW resonators and oscillators by means of equivalent electrical circuits. An equivalent circuit representation of purely elastic nonlinearities in BAW resonators has been developed, and the accuracy of the model in describing the acceleration-induced perturbation in resonator transimpedance has been verified by tests in a unique centrifuge system. The equivalent circuit model has been linked to an oscillator model which includes an empirically derived model of acceleration-sensitive loop components. The calculated acceleration sensitivity of a VCXO modulation oscillator modeled in such a fashion compares favorably with observations.

The second part of this paper discusses practical considerations in the measurement of UHF and microwave frequency sources. The small modulation index approximation of $\beta < 0.1$ corresponds to a sideband-to-carrier ratio $\epsilon(f) \leq -26$ dBc. This limit is regularly exceeded in testing UHF and microwave devices; thus a "moderate" modulation index approximation useful for $\epsilon(f) \leq +10$ dBc has been derived. Another practical consideration concerns the effects of transverse motion in a shake-table system on measurements of the various components of the acceleration sensitivity vector. It has been found that simultaneous measurements of both intended and transverse accelerations of the device under test are required for correct interpretation of the observed frequency shifts. This requirement is particularly evident when the magnitudes of the vector components are substantially unequal.

The final section of this paper presents a derivation of the general conditions for an intrinsically acceleration-insensitive crystal resonator and discusses the application of the

conditions to the evaluation of the relative sensitivity of different crystal cuts, modes of motion, mounting geometries, and piezoelectric materials.

I. Equivalent Electrical Circuit Models

The vector description of the acceleration sensitivity of quartz resonators and oscillators has been widely used during the past decade. The familiar vector equation

$$f(\mathbf{a}) = f(\mathbf{a}=0) \cdot (1 + \Gamma \cdot \mathbf{a}) \quad (1)$$

has been used interchangeably to describe the changes in eigenfrequency of the quartz resonator and operating frequency of the crystal oscillator. That these two quantities are in fact different was first suggested by the data of Valdois, et al. [2], and recently shown conclusively by the measurements of voltage controlled crystal oscillators (VCXO) by Ballato, et al. [3]. This has led to the development of a modeling scheme wherein the effects of acceleration on the quartz resonator and oscillator may be examined separately [4]. That is to say, the acceleration-induced frequency perturbation in a quartz crystal oscillator is well represented by first properly modeling the effects of acceleration on the resonator transimpedance, and then examining the interaction of the perturbed resonator with the oscillator loop. The modeling procedure has been verified experimentally through a series of separate resonator and oscillator tests.

Two separate measurement systems have been employed in this work. Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the shake table system used for VCO tests including recent improvements. The capabilities of this type of system have been described elsewhere [5]. Figure 2 shows a block diagram of the unique centrifugal accelerator system used for resonator tests. This system can produce acceleration levels up to 600g. The linkage of the network analyzer with the centrifuge allows for improved data acquisition and analysis as compared to previous implementations [6]. Although improvements in the commutator and interconnections have been made, commutator related systematic errors present a challenge in measuring the acceleration effects. The accurate determination of the acceleration effects along any resonator axis requires two tests taking advantage of the change in sign associated with the acceleration-induced perturbation when the angle between the applied acceleration and the resonator sensitivity vector is changed by π radians. Figures 3 through 6 show typical test results and data analysis for a centrifugal test system measurement of

Figure 1. Shake table test system.

the perturbation in the scattering matrix element S_{11} of a 30MHz AT-cut crystal in an HC-6 type enclosure.

The Butterworth-Van Dyke single-mode lumped element approximate equivalent electrical circuit is well known. The equivalent circuit parameters may be determined from the crystal material properties using well known relations obtained using the linear piezoelectric theory for the case of the infinite flat plate:

$$C_0 = \frac{\epsilon A}{2 h} \quad (2)$$

$$R_1 = \frac{n^2 \pi^2 h}{4 A e^2} \eta_s = \frac{n^2 \pi^2 h \bar{c} \tau_1}{4 A e^2} \quad (3)$$

$$L_1 = \frac{h^3 \rho}{A e^2} \quad (4)$$

$$C_1 = \frac{4 A e^2}{n^2 \pi^2 h \bar{c}} \quad (5)$$

The point of note is that R_1 and C_1 depend on \bar{c} , while C_0 and L_1 do not. Since the acceleration-induced effects are considered to arise out of purely elastic nonlinearities, one is led to consider the effect of introducing an acceleration sensitive elastic stiffness in these relations. Recognizing that the piezoelectric contribution to the stiffened elastic constant is small in the case of quartz resonators, we model the acceleration sensitive elastic stiffness as

$$\bar{c}(\mathbf{a}) = \bar{c}(\mathbf{a}=0) * (1 + \gamma \cdot \mathbf{a}) \quad (6)$$

wherein we use the lower case Greek gamma to denote the acceleration sensitivity of the elastic stiffness. The relationship between the acceleration sensitivity γ of the elastic stiffness and the acceleration sensitivity Γ of the resonance frequency is simply $\gamma \approx 2 \Gamma$. The perturbations in the various circuit elements follow directly from the substitution of equation (6) into equations (2) through (5). We find

$$C_0(\mathbf{a}) = C_0 \quad (7)$$

$$R_1(\mathbf{a}) = R_1(\mathbf{a}=0) * (1 + \gamma \cdot \mathbf{a}) \quad (8)$$

Figure 2. Centrifugal test system.

Figure 3. Perturbation in $|S_{11}|$ for an AT-cut resonator for $|\mathbf{a}| \approx 600g$ applied as shown. The marker is at the $|\mathbf{a}| = 0$ resonance frequency.

Figure 4. Perturbation in $|S_{11}|$ for the resonator of Figure 3 for $|\mathbf{a}| \approx 600g$ after reversing the resonator orientation as shown.

Figure 5. Systematic offset recovered from the $|S_{11}|$ data of Figures 3 and 4. Scales are the same as Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 6. Perturbation in $|S_{11}|$ recovered from the data of Figures 3 and 4. Scales are the same as Figures 3 and 4.

$$L_1(\mathbf{a}) = L_1 \quad (9)$$

$$C_1(\mathbf{a}) = C_1(\mathbf{a}=0) * (1 - \gamma \cdot \mathbf{a}) \quad (10)$$

These relations may then be used to calculate the crystal resonator transimpedance under acceleration.

The perturbation in S_{11} as calculated using this model for the one-port reflection measurement of Figures 3 through 6 is shown in Figure 7. We note that the calculations involve small differences in large numbers and are near the limits of the numerical precision for our computer. Nevertheless, the modeled perturbation shows the same shape and nearly the same bandwidth in frequency space as the data.

Once the perturbation in resonator transimpedance is known, it is a simple task to obtain the corresponding frequency shift and acceleration sensitivity of an ideal oscillator employing such a resonator as

$$|\Gamma| = - \frac{[\phi(\mathbf{a}) - \phi(\mathbf{a}=0)]}{2 |\mathbf{a}| Q_L} \quad (11)$$

where $\phi(\mathbf{a})$ and $\phi(\mathbf{a}=0)$ are the perturbed and unperturbed phase of the resonator transimpedance, and Q_L is the loaded or phase slope Q of the resonator at the operating point. Implicit in equation (11) is that no other components in the oscillator loop are perturbed by the acceleration. For actual hardware implementations, this is not always true.

The calculated acceleration sensitivity for the ideal case with no loop component contributions other than the crystal resonator is shown in Figure 8. The corresponding resonator S_{21} response is shown in Figure 9. The calculations imply that if the resonator is operated in the vicinity of resonance or antiresonance the overall oscillator acceleration sensitivity will depend on the actual operating point. We have not at this point determined whether this result accurately represents the physical process being modeled, or if it is instead an artifact of the calculational routine as implemented on our computer. We are continuing to examine this issue.

In the case where other loop components are also sensitive to the external acceleration, the effects on the oscillator loop are well represented by an ideal amplifier in series with an acceleration sensitive load reactance. Based on experimental observations, we treat the load reactance as an ideal component with an acceleration sensitive lead inductance as shown in Figure 10. The effect on the lead inductance may be modeled as a linear perturbation in similar

Figure 7. Calculated perturbation in the magnitude of S_{11} for the 30MHz resonator of Figures 3 through 6 with $|\Gamma| = 6 \times 10^{-9}/g$ as $|\mathbf{a}|$ varies between 0 and 500g.

Figure 8. Acceleration sensitivity of an ideal tunable oscillator in which only the resonator transimpedance is acceleration sensitive. For this resonator, $|\Gamma|$ is nominally $2.2 \times 10^{-9}/g$.

Figure 9. S_{21} response for the resonator of Figure 8.

fashion to equation (6), and the perturbation in transimpedance phase of the resonator/series load reactance combination may be employed in equation (11) to obtain the oscillator acceleration sensitivity under various operating conditions.

Figure 11 compares the application of this modeling technique to a crystal VCO incorporating the resonator of Figures 8 and 9 with the measured data obtained for the unit. The results obtained using the equivalent circuit approach are in good agreement with the measured data. The importance of maximizing the resonator loaded Q in order to minimize the effects arising from other loop components is evident in this figure. The importance of applying good construction techniques is also clearly illustrated.

In summary, an equivalent electrical circuit model of the acceleration sensitivity of piezoelectric plate resonators has been derived based on the linear piezoelectric theory, and the accuracy of the model in describing both resonator and oscillator behavior has been verified experimentally. The equivalent circuit modeling approach should prove particularly helpful in analyzing dual-resonator and other acceleration sensitivity compensation schemes. For SAW, SBAW, and similar resonators, the relations corresponding to equations (2) through (5) are more complicated, however the procedure for incorporating acceleration sensitivity in these equivalent circuit models follows directly from the derivation given here.

II. Practical Measurement Considerations

Sinusoidal vibration testing with a system similar to that of Figure 1 provides a convenient means to measure the acceleration sensitivity of a crystal oscillator. It follows directly from equation (1) and FM theory that the crystal oscillator output under sinusoidal vibration will be a frequency modulated signal with modulation index β given by

$$\beta = \frac{(\Gamma \cdot \mathbf{A}) \cdot f_0}{f_v} \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{A} is the peak acceleration vector, f_0 is the unperturbed oscillator output frequency, and f_v is the frequency of the applied sinusoidal vibration. The n^{th} FM sideband ($-\infty \leq \text{integer } n \leq +\infty$) is located at an offset frequency of $n \cdot f_v$ from the carrier and has a magnitude relative to the carrier given by

$$\epsilon_{V_n}^n \{\text{decimal}\} = [J_n(\beta) / J_0(\beta)]^2 \quad (13)$$

or

Figure 10. Empirically determined model of an acceleration sensitive loop component. The vector δ represents the acceleration sensitivity of the component leads.

Figure 11. Measured and calculated acceleration sensitivity of an actual VCO employing the resonator of Figure 8 and 9.

$$\epsilon_{V_n}^n \{\text{dBc}\} = 20 \cdot \log[J_n(\beta) / J_0(\beta)] \quad (14)$$

where the $J_n(\beta)$ are Bessel functions of the first kind of order n and argument β . For "precision" frequency sources in the low r.f. range, the modulation index β is typically less than 0.1 which enables the use of the small index approximation

$$\begin{aligned} J_0(\beta) &= 1 & ; & \quad \beta < 0.1 \\ J_1(\beta) &= \beta/2 & ; & \quad \beta < 0.1 \\ J_n(\beta) &= 0 & ; & \quad \beta < 0.1, n > 2 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

as popularized by Filler [7]. The small modulation index approximation is convenient in eliminating the need to employ Bessel functions but is limited in usefulness by the fact that $\beta=0.1$ corresponds to a first sideband-to-carrier ratio of $\epsilon_{V_1}^1(f) \leq -26$ dBc. This limit is regularly exceeded in testing UHF and microwave frequency sources.

In order to develop a "moderate" index approximation useful for larger sideband levels, we turn to the work of Onoe on quotients of Bessel functions [8]. Onoe defines the quotient function of the first kind $T_\nu(z)$ as

$$T_\nu(z) \equiv \frac{z J_{\nu-1}(z)}{J_\nu(z)} \quad (16)$$

and gives the continued fraction expansion as

$$T_\nu(z) = 2\nu - \frac{z^2}{2 \cdot (\nu+1) - \frac{z^2}{2 \cdot (\nu+2) - \dots}} \quad (17)$$

Substitution of $z=\beta$ and $\nu=1$ into equations (16) and (17) leads to the result that

$$\frac{J_1(\beta)}{J_0(\beta)} = \frac{\beta}{2 - \frac{\beta^2}{4 - \frac{\beta^2}{6 - \frac{\beta^2}{8 - \dots}}}} \quad (18)$$

The moderate modulation index approximation is obtained by truncation of the infinite series in the denominator as

$$\frac{J_1(\beta)}{J_0(\beta)} \approx \frac{4\beta}{8 - \beta^2} \quad (19)$$

This approximation is typically better than an order of magnitude more accurate than the small modulation index approximation over the range $-26 \text{ dBc} \leq \epsilon_V^1(f) \leq +10 \text{ dBc}$. We have chosen $\epsilon_V^1(f) = +10 \text{ dBc}$ as a practical upper limit for the moderate modulation index approximation. Above this level the error in the approximation exceeds 10 per cent. It is a simple matter to extend the approximations by retaining additional terms of the series in the denominator when higher accuracy or greater range is required.

In order to use the moderate modulation index approximation in practical measurements we employ the following procedure:

(1) Measure the first sideband-to-carrier ratio $\epsilon_V^1(f)$ in units of dBc using the spectrum analyzer.

(2) Convert the data to decimal format using

$$\{J_1(\beta)/J_0(\beta)\}_{\text{decimal}} = 10^{[\epsilon_V^1(f)/20]} \quad (20)$$

(3) Determine the modulation index β from

Figure 12. Measured acceleration sensitivity of a 250 MHz SAW oscillator for the vector component normal to the SAW propagation plane.

Figure 13. Measured acceleration sensitivity of a 250 MHz SAW oscillator for the in-plane vector component transverse to the SAW propagation direction.

Figure 14. Measured acceleration sensitivity of a 250 MHz SAW oscillator for the in-plane vector component parallel to the SAW propagation direction.

$$\beta = \frac{-2 + (4 + 8 \cdot [J_1(\beta)/J_0(\beta)]^2)^{1/2}}{[J_1(\beta)/J_0(\beta)]} \quad (21)$$

(4) Determine the acceleration sensitivity vector component magnitude Γ_i from

$$\Gamma_i = \frac{\beta \cdot f_v}{|A| \cdot f_o} \quad (22)$$

In the majority of SAW oscillators tested by the authors, the component of the acceleration sensitivity vector normal to the SAW propagation plane is approximately an order of magnitude larger than either of the in-plane components [3,5,9,10]. In such cases, the effects of transverse motion of the device under test in the shake-table/test fixture system must be considered. This is clearly appreciated by expressing the fractional frequency shift experienced by the accelerated oscillator in component form,

$$\Delta f/f_o = \Gamma \cdot A = \Gamma_x A_x + \Gamma_y A_y + \Gamma_z A_z \quad (23)$$

We observe that the largest product $\Gamma_i A_i$ will dominate the measured response. If one vector component is substantially larger than the others, even a small acceleration along that axis will dominate the measured response. This is illustrated in Figures 12 through 16.

Figure 12 presents the data obtained for a 250 MHz SAW oscillator, converted from sideband levels to acceleration sensitivity using equations (20) through (22), for the vector component normal to the SAW propagation plane. We have confidence in the accuracy of this data because (1) the magnitude of the vector component being measured is large, and (2) our test fixture does not experience transverse motion in this test orientation. Figures 13 and 14 present the "data" obtained for the two in-plane vector components. For these two tests, however, our test fixture experiences measurable transverse motion along an axis parallel to the normal component of the acceleration sensitivity vector of the device under test. We therefore measure the acceleration levels along both the intended test axis and the axis of transverse motion during each test, and use the normal vector component data and measured transverse acceleration in equations (12), (19), and (14) to calculate the sideband levels associated with the transverse motion. Figures 15 and 16 compare the calculated transverse acceleration sideband levels to the measured sideband levels for the tests of Figures 13 and 14. In both cases, the measured sideband levels are nearly the same as those associated with the transverse motion, and the "data" can only

Figure 15. Comparison of measured sideband levels (solid line) and sideband levels generated by transverse motion in the shake-table/test fixture system (dashed line) for the test of Figure 13.

Figure 16. Comparison of measured sideband levels (solid line) and sideband levels generated by transverse motion in the shake-table/test fixture system (dashed line) for the test of Figure 14.

be taken as representing an upper bound for the vector component in question.

III. General Conditions for Intrinsically Acceleration Insensitive Crystal Resonators

The shift in eigenfrequency of a piezoelectric resonator subjected to a biasing condition may be found using the perturbation integral formulation of Tiersten [11], which we reproduce here for completeness as

$$\omega = \omega_\mu - \Delta_\mu \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta_\mu = H_\mu / 2\omega_\mu \quad (25)$$

$$H_\mu = - \int_V \hat{c}_{L7M\alpha} g_{\alpha,M}^\mu g_{7,L}^\mu dV \quad (26)$$

In equations (24) through (26), ω and ω_0 are respectively the perturbed and unperturbed eigenfrequencies, the $\hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha}$ are coefficients dependent on the biasing field, g_α^μ denotes the normalized mode shape, and the integral is taken over the undeformed volume of the piezoelectric plate. If the biasing deformation and mode shape are known, the frequency shift can readily be calculated.

Recent analyses by various authors have focused on the role of symmetry in resonator mounting and mode shape in order to obtain acceleration-insensitive crystal resonator designs [12-29]. The practical limitation of such designs is how well the required symmetry conditions can be reproduced in a production environment. It would be preferable to develop a resonator design wherein acceleration insensitivity is obtained independently of both mounting and mode shape. We are thus led to examine the perturbation integral for a set of general conditions, independent of the biasing state and mode shape, wherein the resulting integral is identically zero.

We begin our analysis by noting that for any mode of motion, there must exist some non-zero mode shape g_α^μ . Thus any zeros of the perturbation integral must be associated with the biasing coefficients $\hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha}$. The defining relation for the biasing coefficients is

$$\hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha} = T_{LM}^1 \delta_{\gamma\alpha} + \zeta_{L\gamma M\alpha KN} E_{KN}^1 + \zeta_{L\gamma KM} w_{\alpha,K} + \zeta_{LK M\alpha} w_{\gamma,K} \quad (27)$$

In equation (27), the $c_{L\gamma KM}$ and $c_{LK M\alpha}$ are the "ordinary" second order elastic stiffnesses while the $c_{L\gamma M\alpha KN}$ are the "non-linear" third order stiffnesses. The terms $w_{\alpha,K}$ and $w_{\gamma,K}$ represent the biasing deformation gradients, and describe the physical deformation of the piezoelectric plate in response to the bias. T_{LM}^1 and E_{KN}^1 represent respectively the static biasing stress and strain and are defined as

$$T_{LM}^1 = \zeta_{LMKN} E_{KN}^1 \quad (28)$$

and

$$E_{KN}^1 = \frac{1}{2} (w_{K,N} + w_{N,K}) \quad (29)$$

Equation (29) is substituted into equation (28) to obtain

$$T_{LM}^1 = \frac{1}{2} \zeta_{LMKN} (w_{K,N} + w_{N,K}) \quad (30)$$

and equations (29) and (30) are substituted into equation (27) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha} = & \frac{1}{2} \zeta_{LMKN} (w_{K,N} + w_{N,K}) \delta_{\gamma\alpha} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \zeta_{L\gamma M\alpha KN} (w_{K,N} + w_{N,K}) \\ & + \zeta_{L\gamma KM} w_{\alpha,K} + \zeta_{LK M\alpha} w_{\gamma,K} \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

We can combine terms and employ the symmetry of the stiffness tensors to rewrite equation (31) as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha} = & w_{N,K} [\zeta_{L\gamma M\alpha KN} + \zeta_{LMKN} \delta_{\gamma\alpha} \\ & + \zeta_{L\gamma KM} \delta_{\alpha N} + \zeta_{LK M\alpha} \delta_{\gamma N}] \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The bracketed terms represent a set of stiffness cofactors dependent only upon the material properties of the piezoelectric plate. Defining the stiffness cofactors $k_{L\gamma M\alpha KN}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} k_{L\gamma M\alpha KN} = & [\zeta_{L\gamma M\alpha KN} + \zeta_{LMKN} \delta_{\gamma\alpha} \\ & + \zeta_{L\gamma KM} \delta_{\alpha N} + \zeta_{LK M\alpha} \delta_{\gamma N}] \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

we may rewrite equation (32) as

$$\hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha} = w_{N,K} k_{L\gamma M\alpha KN} \quad (34)$$

The general conditions for an intrinsically acceleration-insensitive crystal resonator are now clearly understood:

If for each coefficient $\hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha}$, the stiffness cofactors $k_{L\gamma M\alpha KN}$ of the deformation gradients $w_{N,K}$ are zero, then the eigenfrequency of the resonator will be independent of the biasing state and mode shape.

In the most general case, there are 81 $\hat{c}_{L\gamma M\alpha}$ each of which contains 9 stiffness cofactors for a total of 729 independent conditions which must be met for the resonator to be intrinsically acceleration-insensitive. The number of independent conditions which must be met for any particular resonator will be reduced by the symmetry class of the piezoelectric material, and may be further reduced by both mounting structure and mode shape.

As an example of the mounting structure reducing the number of required conditions, we consider the case of a SAW substrate rigidly and uniformly supported along its back surface. The substrate deformation in response to an acceleration is then limited to thickness extension or thickness shear only. In this case, the

number of allowed deformation gradients is reduced from nine to three.

As an example of the mode shape reducing the number of required conditions, we consider the case of rotated Y-cut quartz BAW resonators operating in the slow thickness-shear mode. The mode shape varies slowly enough in the lateral dimensions that the only mode displacement gradient required for the perturbation integral is $g_{1,2}^H$, and thus the only biasing coefficient required is c_{1212} [17]. There are then only nine conditions required to achieve intrinsic acceleration insensitivity for an arbitrarily mounted resonator of this type. In Figures 17 through 21, the five non-zero k_{1212KN} are plotted as a function of orientation angle θ for the family of rotated Y-cut quartz resonators.

Figure 17. The cofactor k_{121211} versus orientation angle for rotated Y-cut quartz.

Figure 18. The cofactor k_{121222} versus orientation angle for rotated Y-cut quartz.

Figure 19. The cofactor k_{121223} versus orientation angle for rotated Y-cut quartz.

Figure 20. The cofactor k_{121232} versus orientation angle for rotated Y-cut quartz.

Figure 21. The cofactor k_{121233} versus orientation angle for rotated Y-cut quartz.

There are a number of observations to be made regarding the intrinsic insensitivity conditions:

(1) The statement of the general conditions represents a set of criteria for which a material may be searched. It does not constitute proof that the conditions can be met.

(2) This analysis is valid only to the order of the approximations underlying the perturbation theory. The conditions as stated should be sufficient to determine the existence of zeros in a region of crystal orientations, however a higher order analysis may be required to precisely determine exact loci.

(3) The general conditions have been derived for an arbitrary static biasing deformation and an arbitrary mode shape. They are applicable not only to the problem of acceleration sensitivity, but to other stress- and deformation-induced phenomena such as the contributions of electrode and mounting stress relief to aging.

(4) The general conditions shed light on the misconception that acceleration sensitivity arises from the fact that the piezoelectric material is nonlinear. The cofactors $k_{L/MoKN}$ contain sums of both second- and third-order stiffnesses. In a perfectly linear material, the third-order stiffness terms vanish but not the second-order terms. Thus while material nonlinearity is a significant part of acceleration sensitivity, there is also a "linear" part arising solely from the physical deformation of the resonator shape.

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